

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14272080

Occupational Incentives And Teachers' Retention In Private Secondary Schools In Rivers State, Nigeria

Isaac, Esther Uwem

**Department of Educational Management
Faculty of Education
University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt, Nigeria
Isaacesther48@gmail.com**

ABSTRACT

This study examined occupational incentives and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State. The study had three objectives, with corresponding research questions and null hypotheses. It adopted correlational research design, with population which comprised of 8,500 teachers in all the 1,415 accredited private secondary schools in Rivers State. A sample size of 382 respondents were drawn for the study using Taro Yamane, while stratified sampling technique was adopted as technique for the study. The instrument was a questionnaire of two sets, titled: Occupational Incentives Assessment Scale (OIAS) and Teachers' Retention Assessment Scale (TRAS). The instrument was validated and reliability coefficients of 0.82 and 0.87 were obtained for both instruments respectively using Cronbach alpha reliability statistics. The research questions were answered using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistics, while the hypotheses were tested using z-ratio at 0.05 level of significance. Findings of the study revealed that there is a high positive and significant relationship between professional development, work safety, recognition and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State. It was concluded that occupational incentives relate with teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers Stat. Based on the findings and conclusion, it was recommended among others that, proprietors of private schools should work hand in hand with the government to continually provide professional development programmes for teachers in their schools to enhance their teaching skills. Also, government should always look at private school managers' internal policies and procedures governing work safety to ensure it effective implementation.

Keywords: Occupational Incentives, Teacher Retention, Private Secondary Schools

INTRODUCTION

The educational policy of any nation such as Nigeria is to achieve education for all. The priority is to ensure equitable access and improvement in the quality and efficiency of education at all levels. All these indicate that education seeks to nourish the good qualities in man and bring out the best in every individual. Secondary school is the education children attend after primary school and before the tertiary stage within the range of 12-18 years (FRN, 2013). Specifically, the secondary school system is geared towards catering for the differences in talents, provision for technical knowledge and vocational skills necessary for agricultural, industrial, commercial and economic development. As stated in the national policy on education (FRN, 2013), secondary education has two distinct objectives: preparing students for higher education and preparing students for useful living in the society.

For qualitative secondary education to be achieved in a nation, the teacher (human resource) must be well trained, supervised and taken care of, because they are the ones who facilitate learning. Teachers whether at the public or private secondary schools support, observe and record the progress of

students (Adebayo, 2019). Teachers must be properly managed and taken care of in order to keep them up to date with developments in their subject areas, new resources, methods and national objectives in the educational sector and above retain them in the job. Without appropriate management of teachers, especially in the area of their welfare, retaining them in the job will be a mirage.

Teacher retention refers to the proportion of teachers in one year who are still teaching in the same school till the following year. It relates to the goal of keeping teachers in the workplace, and reducing their turnover (Agabi & Akpomi, 2019). Teacher retention is defined as the capacity to keep, trained teachers in the teaching profession and in their posted teaching locations and schools up to their retirement age. It is defined as teachers leaving their schools or school districts, but staying within the teaching profession. When quality teachers leave their schools the result is a shortage of effective teachers which in turn impedes student learning and other school activities. It has been reported that teachers that leave their schools for different employment opportunities are characteristically more effective teacher. This is because they get better packages or incentives in their new place of work (Jacob & Lefgen, 2022). The flight of quality teachers hurts all students and schools. Cha and Vogel (2021) asserted that teachers attrition has never done any school good, rather it retard the activities of schools. For schools to have a full grip of her teachers at all time, Cha and Vogel (2021) opined that attractive occupational incentives should be provided or made available for them.

Teacher retention is a key subject in education productiveness. While teachers are not just expected to leave their job, it is also expedient that they perform all their tasks with show of commitment to the job. Teacher retention in other words means dedication to doing what is required for the achievement of predetermined goals. Teacher retention therefore refers to the willingness of teachers to stay in their job and give their best towards the achievement of the goals of the school where they work. A teacher who remains in his place of work is self-motivated; he is one that enjoys his job and shows signs of job satisfaction. Teacher retention is idiosyncratic. It varies from one teacher to another. It therefore could account for the differences in the productivity and performance of different teachers working in the same or different schools. A retained teacher is likely to be more productive and resourceful as a teacher than a teacher who wants (Igbogi, 2019).

However, the retention of a teacher must come with the relevant occupational incentives in order to achieve increased productivity. The indicators of teacher retention may include regular attendance to school, punctuality to school, effective classroom management, resourcefulness in usage of instructional materials in delivery of instruction, participation in extracurricular activities for development of students, teaching the required number of classes stipulated for the week, writing of lesson notes, evaluation of students during and after delivery of instruction, adhere to ethical and professional standards, acting as loco parentis to students, collaborating with colleagues to enhance service delivery, engaging in professional development programmes to enhance capacity and productivity (Inim, 2021).

Occupational incentives can be any reward or programme introduced in the workplace to develop and encourage employees performance and stimulate retention. Occupational incentives describe a system of rewarding success and effort in the workplace by allowing employees like teachers to earn prizes or recognition (Igbogi, 2019). In the school system, occupational incentives refer to policies, programmes or reward mapped out for workers like the teachers in the school. These incentives when properly implemented reinforces positive behavior in the teacher, stimulate performance, inspire productivity, and as well help keep them in the job (Inim, 2021).

Occupational incentives are management tools or strategies to influence the attitude and commitment of teachers to remain in the school system. The Skinner's reinforcement theory posits that occupational incentives can be used for operant behavioural conditioning. Reinforcement theory shows how the consequence of past behaviour affects future actions in a recurrent learning process. This means that incentives which teachers receive determine their future attitude and retention in the job. In line with this, Oladele (2023) observed that occupational incentives are offered after the job had been completed and after the employer had approved their work. At the same time rewards can also be offered before the work is done and is aimed at improving performance of employees in this case teachers who are not meeting expected standard or established goals.

Furthermore, occupational incentives can be in form of monetary or non-monetary. Monetary occupational incentives may be in the form of salary, bonuses and allowances while non-monetary occupational incentives include promotions, paid time off, recognition/appreciation, work safety and flexible work hours (Jubril, (2021). Yazdani, et al (2019) also posited that there are two kinds of occupational incentives that have particular relevance to boosting teachers' retention. They identified them as monetary incentives (which may be direct or indirect) and non-monetary incentives. Direct monetary incentives include salaries, cash tied to specific performance, behaviour or condition while the indirect monetary incentives include other financial resources that are used as reward like professional support (training) and flexible work hours. The non-monetary incentives however, could be compensation reward, recognition reward, appreciation reward and many more.

Occupational incentives could be measured on how teachers perceive their job and how they assert themselves in their roles and responsibilities. According to Bello and Adebayo (2021) the components of include: trainings, promotion, good salary, flexible working hours, allowances, job security, better offices and work space. Concurring to the view of Bello and Adebayo (2021). Andrews and Erwin as cited in Inim (2021) also asserted that components of occupational incentives are professional development, work safety, recognition, allowances, flexible working hours, promotion and many others. But for the purpose of this study we will be considering professional development, work safety and recognition.

Professional development as a component of occupational incentives simply means workers education and continued learning. In the case of the school organization, Fafunwa in Ayeni (2021) views teacher professional development as the teaching and training experiences provided not only within teacher institutions but also outside them with the basic aim of preparing and grooming potential teachers for teaching activities. As observed by Ita (2019), it is not just enough to recruit teachers for the programme, but to provide continuous in-service programme or development programmes for the teachers to update their knowledge, skills and competence for them to function effectively and efficiently. While Fullan in Ayeni (2021) conceives teacher professional development as the sum total of formal and informal learning pursued and experienced by the teacher in a compelling learning environment under conditions of complexity and dynamic change. A common underpinning assertion of the above definitions is continuing learning process, by which serving teachers acquire the knowledge, skills and values to sustain the desired spark of intellectual vitality, which will improve the quality of teaching, students' learning outcomes and their confidence to remain in the teaching job.

Furthermore, work safety which is another components of occupational incentives is referred to the working environment encompassing all factors that impact the safety, health, and well-being of employees. In the school system, it has to do with the work environment of the teachers, which is concerned with their employers eliminating injuries, risks, and hazards (Safe and Sound School, 2021). In the case of the school workplace, Hernandez et al., as cited by Mubita et al. (2022) viewed work safety as a school free from violence, where no perceived fear exist in the school. It simply means that the school safety is considered as safe when it supports teaching and learning in a way that both staff and students including visitors can freely interact without fear or threats. Hull as cited in Mubita et al. (2022) advanced school safety from management perspective stating it encompasses the school's culture, training and resources provided to respond appropriately to threats and hazards in the school. This approaches views school safety as first a direct responsibility of school management before any other person or group. The school workplace safety is the responsibility of an employer to take all safety measures to provide a healthy working condition to all teachers and a risk-free environment that encourages the teachers to stay in their job.

Recognition is another occupational incentives which secondary school teachers receive. It refers to the public acknowledgement of the contribution made by an employee towards the attainment of organizational goal. It is suitable for satisfying the egoistic and self-actualization need of workers. In Hierarchy of Need theory, Maslow noted that workers bring these needs to the workplace and would work only if they would be rewarded with these needs. Teachers are human beings with emotions and feelings. They (like other workers), have such egoistic and self- actualization needs thus they work even harder to ensure that students perform better in the continuous assessment and internal/external examinations (Inim, 2021). Apart from classroom teaching and learning task, teachers undertake other

responsibilities within the school systems. They involve in the school extracurricular activities, serve in committees supervise students and social activities. Most teachers even put in extra hours of work in other to help slow learners with areas where they may be having difficulties. The volume of work of an average teacher is quite enormous due to inadequate supply of subject teachers in most schools. Given the above situation, it is imperative that teachers are recognized to encourage them stay in their job.

Consequently, it is important to note that discouraged teachers who are deprived of good job incentives as identified above may see it that they are being drained in a school system, and many a time it may be difficult to retain them in the job. Teachers with unhealthy attitude often are symptoms of unhealthy school management practices. Million (2021) believed that traditional, rigid, bureaucratically administered schools result in low teacher commitment and retention. Progressive and flexible schools that implement great occupational incentives promote teachers' feeling of affiliation with the school and retention. In the more flexible schools, teachers believe they can contribute to positive school wide changes and that their contributions will be sought after and valued. Teachers who are satisfied with their jobs also have a high degree of morale. They feel qualified in terms of their knowledge of subject matter and their teaching skills, and they feel secure about classroom management.

In a progressive and flexible school atmosphere, Million (2021) asserts that teachers have more satisfaction and higher professional commitment. In schools where the atmosphere is tense and where teachers feel isolated, they tend to have lower commitment resulting in teachers attrition. Labour is indeed mobile and teachers more especially those who work in the private schools are in constant search for better opportunities in terms of the degree to which their needs would be met. Like every other employees, public secondary school teachers in Nigeria, are constantly hunting for more rewarding job opportunities. Contingent on the above background, the researcher investigated whether there exist any relationship between occupational incentives (proxied by professional development, work safety, recognition) and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

To ensure that commitment is sustained amongst teachers who are employees in school is one of the fundamental responsibilities of educational managers. Personal observation by the researcher shows that some teachers demonstrate low level of commitment in carrying out the task of which they have sworn an oath to protect, which resulted in their attrition. Sometimes, the teachers get dissatisfied about their job due to ill treatment meted against them. These dissatisfaction expressed by these teachers many times obstruct classroom effectiveness and output. This scenario as observed is the fortune of most private schools in Rivers State. Owing to certain conditions in the private teaching profession, teachers at that level have been seen complaining, exhibiting dissatisfaction and tendency to quit their job in search for some other kind of job or in search of other schools where they feel that their welfare will be fully regarded or they will not experience some unfavourable working conditions.

These unfavourable working conditions which among others include lack of professional development programmes, workplace safety and recognition of teachers' effort. Teachers in private schools in Rivers State have been reported to be the least rewarded workers despite their high volume of work input, critical role and contributions towards the development their schools. The issue of teachers' re-occurring truancy, lateness to work and absenteeism could be traceable to lack of job (occupational) incentives. Therefore, the researcher was bothered whether there is a relationship between these incentives and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State. Hence, the problem of the study.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to examine the relationship between occupational incentives and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives sought to:

1. determine the relationship between professional development and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. ascertain the relationship between work safety and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State.
3. investigate the relationship between recognition and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the relationship between professional development and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State?

2. What is the relationship between work safety and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State?
3. What is the relationship between recognition and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance guided the study.

1. There is no significant relationship between professional development and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant relationship between work safety and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State.
3. There is no significant relationship between recognition and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a correlation survey design to ascertain the relationship between independent variable (occupational incentives) and dependent variable (teachers' retention). The population of the study consisted of eight thousand, five hundred (8,500) teachers in 1,415 private secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. The sample size for this study was 382 teachers drawn from the population using Taro Yamane. The sampling technique was stratified sampling technique, while the research instrument was a questionnaire of two sets, titled: Occupational Incentives Assessment Scale (OIAS) and Teachers' Retention Assessment Scale (TRAS). The instrument has two sections (A and B). Section A elicited demographic information from the respondents, while section B prompted items on research question one to three. The items of the instrument are responded on a 4-point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). Data used for this study were sourced primarily by the researcher and with the help of two research assistants. 382 copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents, after which 369 copies were retrieved and found suitable for analysis resulting in approximately 97% retrieval rate. Cronbach alpha reliability statistics was used to calculate the reliability coefficients of the two questionnaire which yielded an index of 0.82 and 0.87 for Occupational Incentives Assessment Scale (OIAS) and Teachers' Retention Assessment Scale (TRAS) respectively. For data that were analysed research question one to three were answered using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) formula, while z-ratio statistics was used to test hypotheses one to three at 0.05 level of significance. Correlation coefficients between 0.90 – 1.00 were considered to be a Very High (VH), 0.70 – 0.80 are High (H) while correlation coefficients between 0.50 – 0.60 were Moderate (M) and between 0.30 – 0.40 were Low (L) while below 0.20 (< 0.20) were Very Low (VL).

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between professional development and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis on the Relationship between Professional Development and Teachers' Retention in Private Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Variable	Σ	Σ^2	n	df	ΣXY	r	Decision
Professional Development (X)	1713	22031					
Teacher Retention (Y)	1600	19442	369	367	18429	0.83	High (Positive Relationship)

Source: *Researcher's Field Result, 2024*

Data on Table 1 reveal a correlation coefficient of = 0.83. This value is high and positive, indicating that there is high and positive relationship between professional development and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State. This implies that increase in professional development leads to corresponding increase in teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between work safety and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis on the Relationship between Work Safety and Teachers' Retention in Private Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Variable	Σ	Σ^2	n	df	ΣXY	r	Decision
Work Safety (X)	1755	24118	369	367	19970	0.88	High (Positive Relationship)
Teacher Retention (Y)	1600	19442					

Source: *Researcher's Field Result, 2024*

Data on Table 2 reveal a correlation coefficient of = 0.88. This value is high and positive, indicating that there is high and positive relationship between work safety and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State. This implies that increase in work safety leads to corresponding increase in teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Question 3: *What is the relationship between recognition and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis on the Relationship between Recognition and Teachers' Retention in Private Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Variable	Σ	Σ^2	n	df	ΣXY	r	Decision
Recognition (X)	1802	23117	369	367	19827	0.85	High (Positive Relationship)
Teacher Retention (Y)	1600	19442					

Source: *Researcher's Field Result, 2024*

Data on Table 3 reveal a correlation coefficient of = 0.85. This value is high and positive, indicating that there is high and positive relationship between recognition and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State. This implies that increase in recognition leads to corresponding increase in teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State.

Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between professional development and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: z-ratio on the relationship between professional development and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State

Variable	Σ	Σ^2	n	df	ΣXY	r	z-ratio	z-crit	Decision
Professional Development (X)	1713	22031	369	367	18429	0.83	34.40	1.96	Rejected Ho ₁ (Significant)
Teacher Retention (Y)	1600	19442							

Source: *Researcher's Field Result, 2024*

Data on Table 4 reveal that a high positive relationship exists between professional development and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State. To establish the significance of the relationship, z-ratio was computed and an index of 34.40 was obtained. This was compared to the critical z-critical of 1.96 at the 0.05 level of significance with a degree of freedom of 367, indicating

that there is a significant positive relationship between professional development and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State (calculated $z = 34.40 > \text{critical } z = 1.96$ at $p < 0.05$ and $df = 367$). Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between professional development and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State is rejected.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between work safety and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 5: z-ratio on the relationship between work safety and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State

Variable	Σ	Σ^2	n	df	ΣXY	r	z-ratio	z-crit	Decision
Work Safety (X)	1755	24118							
			369	367	19970	0.88	39.95	1.96	Rejected H_{02} (Significant)
Teacher Retention (Y)	1600	19442							

Source: *Researcher's Field Result, 2024*

Data on Table 5 reveal that a high positive relationship exists between work safety and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State. To establish the significance of the relationship, z-ratio was computed and an index of 39.95 was obtained. This was compared to the critical z-critical of 1.96 at the 0.05 level of significance with a degree of freedom of 367, indicating that there is a significant positive relationship between professional development and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State (calculated $z = 39.95 > \text{critical } z = 1.96$ at $p < 0.05$ and $df = 367$). Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between work safety and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State is rejected.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between recognition and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 6: z-ratio on the relationship between recognition and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State

Variable	Σ	Σ^2	n	df	ΣXY	r	z-ratio	z-crit	Decision
Recognition (X)	1802	23117							
			369	367	19827	0.85	36.20	1.96	Rejected H_{03} (Significant)
Teacher Retention (Y)	1600	19442							

Source: *Researcher's Field Result, 2024*

Data on Table 6 reveal that a high positive relationship exists between recognition and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State. To establish the significance of the relationship, z-ratio was computed and an index of 36.20 was obtained. This was compared to the critical z-critical of 1.96 at the 0.05 level of significance with a degree of freedom of 367, indicating that there is a significant positive relationship between recognition and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State (calculated $z = 36.20 > \text{critical } z = 1.96$ at $p < 0.05$ and $df = 367$). Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between recognition and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State is rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Professional Development and Teachers' Retention in Private Secondary Schools

The first finding of this study revealed that there is high and positive relationship between professional development and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State. Also, the corresponding hypothesis establishes that there is significant relationship between professional development and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State. These finding

corroborates Abbas and Hammadi (2019), Hammam and Al-Maqableh (2019), Ayeni (2020) and Muhsen (2021) whose empirical works showed that there is a positive link between professional development of teachers and their retention in the job. Abbas and Hammadi (2019) in his empirical works observed that high participation of teachers in professional programmes as an incentive made available by school organisation motivates the teachers to perform and remain in their job without thinking of leaving. Hammam and Al-Maqableh (2019) in their empirical studies asserted also that professional development of teacher of private schools was high because the management sees it as a vital incentive or style in improving job retention. In same vein, Muhsen (2021) investigated the level of teachers retention in private schools in Amman; the study attempted to identify the most effective factors that help to retain teachers in the schools. The study found that the percentage of incentive like professional development of teacher was high since it reached 68.82%. These studies have shown the similarities and importance of professional development to an organisation like the school. When teachers are trained it could help to boost their morale to stay in their job.

Work Safety and Teachers' Retention in Private Secondary Schools

The second finding of the study showed that there is high and positive relationship between work safety and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State. Similarly, the corresponding hypothesis tested shows that there is significant relationship between work safety and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State. These findings are similar with Eseyin, et al (2017), Prinsloo (2019), Kreitner (2021), Idowu and Iyabo (2021) who in their empirical studies found out that work safety is a key predictor of teacher retention in school, considering that the teacher needs to feel a sense of security at work before he can function properly in the school less he will withdraw his services and leave the system. Prinsloo (2019) in his empirical studies further observed that a safe school is important for effective teaching and learning as well as teacher retention. The teachers just like workers in other organisations will not be able to risk their lives and welfare for the organization and as such they require protection from harm to be able to work properly in the school. Also in support of the finding, Mohammad and Susanty (2022), and Anggoro et al. (2020) observed in their empirical works that there is a significant influence of work safety on teacher retention; the studies confirm that poor or absence of safety management decreases employee productivity and retention. These have shown the similarities and the need of work safety in the school for teachers. When teachers feel secured safe within their work environment it boost their morale and reduce attrition.

Recognition and Teachers' Retention in Private Secondary Schools

The third finding of the study revealed that there is high and positive relationship between recognition and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State. In addition, the corresponding hypothesis tested establishes that there is significant relationship between work safety and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State. These findings are in consonance with the empirical works of Igbogi (2019), Bello and Adebayo (2021), Njanja e al (2023), who in their various studies found that non-financial incentives like recognition have a high and positive correlation with teacher retention. Also, Employee Recognition (2021) concurred in their own study that recognizing teachers in private schools has proven to have a significant relationship with teacher staying in their job. They added that showing some form of private or public appreciation of teachers in school and giving them credit for their work-related accomplishments or contributions to the school reduces teachers attrition. According to them, it was recommended that recognition of teachers should involve the issuing of plaques and certificates of recognition as well as completing it with some form of monetary and non-monetary incentives. This therefore makes the process meaningful and relevant to the needs of the teachers. Inim (2021), found in his work that recognised teachers have positive attitude towards the school organisation and this help to increase retention. Also, Danish and Usman (2020) in their empirical study found that if the school organisation fails to recognize the specific contributions of their teachers, the teachers will lack the willingness to express creativity and dare challenging task, thereby causing them to leave their job in search of where their efforts will be appreciated and recognised. Hence, these empirical works have shown similarities to this study by identifying the link between recognition and teacher retention. When teachers are recognized, they feel some level of satisfaction in their job, thereby reducing attrition.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the study concluded that there is a high positive and significant relationship between professional development, work safety, recognition as occupational incentives and teachers' retention in private secondary schools in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Proprietors of private schools should work hand in hand with the Government to continually provide professional development programmes for teachers in their schools to enhance their teaching skills.
2. Government should always look at private school managers' internal policies and procedures governing work safety to ensure its effective implementation. This should be strengthened by the government coming up with a regular monitoring team to verify how the schools are doing towards adhering to safety guidelines to ensure teachers' safety.
3. Private school administrators should not downplay the recognition of teachers' efforts especially whenever they do well in order to reduce the level of teachers' attrition in these schools.

REFERENCES

- Abbas, A. & Hammadi, S. (2019). Motivations and their effects on performance. *Tanmiat Alrafidain*, 93(31), 2-19.
- Adebayo, K. (2019). *Principal supervisory techniques for enhanced teachers' job performance in secondary schools in PHALGA, Rivers State*. Unpublished Undergraduate Project Submitted to the Department of Educational Management, University of Port Harcourt.
- Agabi, C. O., & Akpomi, M. E. (2019). *Concepts in the economics of education*. University of Port Harcourt Press.
- Ayeni, A. J. (2020). *Teachers' instructional task performance and principals' supervisory roles as correlates of quality Assurance in Secondary Schools in Ondo State*. Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile – Ife, Nigerian.
- Bello. O. W., & Adebayo, A. A. (2021). Reward system and employees performance in Lagos State. *A Journal of Business and Management Review*, 3 (8), 8-15.
- Danish, R. Q., & Usman, A. (2020). Impact of reward and recognition on job satisfaction and motivation: An empirical study from Pakistan. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 5(2), 159-169.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013). *National policy on education*. NERDC
- Hammam, A. & AL-Maqableh, K. (2019). Factors influence employee satisfaction in Jordanian Hotels. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 3(4), 87-101.
- Idowu, S. A. (2020). Role of flexible working hours' arrangement on teacher job performance and retention in schools in Agbara, Nigeria. *Economic Insights – Trends and Challenges*, 4(67), 23-37.
- Igbogi, I. (2019). Teachers' welfare and commitment as determinant of productivity in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Education*, 11(6), 1041- 1058.
- Inim, W. (2021). *Reward mechanisms as predictors of teacher job commitment in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State*. Unpublished M.Ed. Dissertation Submitted to Postgraduate School, University of Port Harcourt.
- Ita, M. M. (2019). School environment influence on students in secondary schools within Matungulu and Kangundo Districts, Kenya. *International Journal of Science and Research*, 7(10), 796-807.
- Jacob, R., & Lefgen, A. (2022). *Organizational behaviour*. 8th (ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- Kreitner, R. (2021). *Management (10th ed.)*. Houghton Mifflin Company.
- Million, J. (2021). *Honor your teachers*. National association of elementary school principals. <http://www.nbpts.org/contentload>.

Mohammad, A. & Susanty, I. (2022). Relationship between job satisfaction, working conditions
Isaac *Int. J. Innovative Soc. & Sci. Educ. Res.* 12 (4):266-275, 2024

- Mubita, K., Phiri, T. K., Monde, P. N. & Simooya, S. M. (2022). Safety and health issues in selected schools of Chibombo District in Central Province of Zambia. *International Journal of Humanities Social Sciences and Education (IJHSSE)* 3(10), 99-109
- Muhsen, W. (2021). *The extent of employee satisfaction working in UNIRWA in Gaza about incentives and rewards system*. Islamic University Press
- Njanja, W. L., Mama, R. N., Kebet, L. N., & Njagi, (2023). Effect of reward on employee performance: A case of Kenya power and lighting company Ltd. Nakuru, Kenya. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 8(21), 16-25.
- Oladele, M. P. (2023). Relationship between salary, training, conditions of service and job performance of primary school teachers in Ogun State, Nigeria. *Journal of Empirical Research*, 8(7), 57-66.
- Safe and Sound School (2021). *Safety versus Security: What's the difference?*
<https://www.safeandsoundschools.org>
- Yazdani, B. O. Yaghoubi, N. M., & Gin, E. S., (2019). Factors affecting the empowerment of employees. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 20(2), 267-274.